
GREEN IT AND ORGANIZATIONAL PRACTICES IN BANGALORE CITY: EMPLOYEES' PERSPECTIVES

Ms. Tanushree Sodhani

Research Scholar, Amity University UP, India

Prof. (Dr.) Alka Munjal,

Dean (SAASS), Amity University UP, India

Dr. T. R. Venkatesh

VC, Amity University Patna, India

ABSTRACT—

The purpose of this research paper is to examine employees' perceptions on Green IT practices in selected industries of Bangalore city such as IT, ITES and Banking services with the ratio of 3:2:1. This study also seeks at what level employee green behavior (EGB), work values (work values), felt accountability (FA) and green display rules (GDR) are associated with each other on green practices in organizations. The survey completed with 398 valid respondents and data were analyzed for scale reliability test, descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation test. The results found as significant positive association between EGB and work values, felt accountability and green display rules. (r within the range of 0.819-0.943, sig. $p \leq 0.05$). Further research can be conducted with extended area of research and population size.

Key words— Green IT, employee green behavior, work values, felt accountability, green display rules.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Dangers to the earth have facing probably the most significant issues confronting the whole world on environment and considered as a prime problem in the world. Organizational role towards environmental challenges also a crucial one and contributing their level best to cope the problem through going green. In expansion, organizations may profit by expanding deals,

marking acknowledgment, and attractive employee outcomes in the event that they effectively utilize green approaches to advance ecological supportability. Employees are the individuals who execute hierarchical green arrangements; in this way, the most important for companies to be advance and transform their practices as well as pay guarantee that such predictable conduct with authoritative green objectives. Employee behavior aligned with environmental sustainability is referred as green behavior, which includes organizational citizenship behavior for environment and task –oriented pro-environmental behavior. Ones, D.S (2012) studied that green behavior is voluntary in organizations but it is also necessary to adopt behavior linked job tasks and that is why voluntary green job place behavior is also a type of organizational citizenship behavior. Environmental psychologists examined that voluntary green behavior associated with individual characteristics of employees in organization. Such characteristics are personality, leadership and leadership style, employee attitude towards pro-environmental activities, moral obligation and personal values. The present study is centered in employees` green behavior and its reflections on WV, FA and GDR. So that, green behavior is overviewed. Employees` perceptions and interpretations on organizational policies also plays important role in green behavior and such perceptions also known as psychological climate. Employee becomes more responsible on understanding conversion of organizational policies into guidelines regarding environmental sustainability. (Mortan et.al)

In general, work values are subset of ideas as well as beliefs related to employee`s job in organization. It also includes self-respect, respect for others, honesty piece, service, success and commitment to the work. It may differ cultural divergence in the country like India. Some of the behavioral drivers that promotes development of organization and self-achievement. The dimensions of driving factors are such as functional orientation, intrinsic choice, mutual harmony, new ideas oriented openness as well as long-term development. These dimensions are include in structure questionnaire for the survey in the present study.

Felt accountability is associated with employee in contemporary era in corporate world. It is linked with employee outcomes. It may be explained in simple terms as it is a personal responsibility of employee to others. Perceived accountability plays important role in employee green behavior. Employee recognition as well as self-images are also reciprocally associated with each other. Felt accountability is also related with employee job satisfaction. Employee feelings on conscientiousness, agreeableness, emotional stability and openness have positive impacts on job –satisfaction. The present study attempts to measure the association between employee green behavior and felt accountability with reference to IT/ITeS and banking sector of Bangalore city. As a result, it is discuss theoretical background of felt accountability, also. Felt accountability has predicted positive outcomes in several studies but it is also demonstrated as anxieties provoking properties. Several studies also explain that felt accountability impedes favorable outcomes in organizations. (G.R and Zinko, 2009) The relationship between felt accountability and perceived organizational performance are positively associated with each other.(David Andrew,2013)

Green Display Rules (GDR), in general, demonstrates employees` distinguished job demands to display green related behavior in company. In can be said in another form that employees` build their attitudes as well as perceptions on civilization base. In the present study, we considered green display rules (GDR) as perceived job demands in organizations. Employees` perceptions of reciprocal job demands inherent within GDR may depend on managers` opinion on how employees are valuable in organization.

Social data preparing hypothesis proposes that employee impression of employment requests are affected by what individuals around them think. At the end of the day, representatives manufacture their recognitions and perspectives in the public arena dependent on expressive gestures in the work environment which acts their conduct For instance, bosses

who place more noteworthy significance on relational employment requests may flag to employees that employees are essentially associated the with activities and afterward employees can reflect their bosses' concerns and give better consideration to relational parts of employee activity. The importance and significance of relational work necessities can trigger employee self-guideline exercises to screen their own consistence with GDR. In this manner, logical factors, for example, display rules assume a significant job in enacting esteems and reinforcing or debilitating values to behavior relationship.

That is, the point at which an individual representative's job esteems are steady with the given GDR leads, their values are seen as worthy and supported in the association, which encourage their values confirmation and thusly fortify the qualities to-behavior relationship. Then again, if employees' work values are seen as socially inappropriate in organization.

Thus, these four factors can be shown in the following framework (fig.1) within the scope of the present study.

Figure 1 Four factors

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Triandis (1980) studied on green behavioral intentions of employees becomes mandatory and they bound to behave in certain ways towards green environmental activities promoted by organization. Greaves, Zibarras and Stride (2013) also remarked that employees' green behavior intentions involve them to self-set goals to act in environmentally responsible ways at work place. It is also to be taken into consider that individual personality cannot be ignored in such kind of green environment practices. Dumont, Shen & Deng (2016) studied that green psychological climate is important in any organization. Employees are also to be aware of organizational policies, organizational procedures, and organizational practices regarding environmental sustainability. Norton et al (2014) studied on green behavior that corporate environmental strategy is positively associated with green psychological climate.

Burdi A et al (2015) explained work values as values are a goals choice and parameters of long-term stability which are associated with cultural, social and personality Erez and Earley (1993), studied in an article titled as "cultural self-presentation theory" cope with the question of how cultural values and factors can account for the fact that managerial influences such as goal-setting, job enrichment, quality-circles, performance-based pay have put off for a further time so greatly in effectiveness between nations. The theory points at the moderator effect of values the relations between general values and work values are being considered in various manners. One view is that values have a specific subjective structure which delivers a basic similitude between general qualities and work esteems.

Hou X et al (2014) studied that when working in a situation that coordinates their self-values, representatives with characteristic inclination will have more prominent worth check and, thus, participate in unselfish green conduct predictable with positive self-sees. At the point

when utilitarian-situated worker has a high long haul direction, he/she hopes to get open doors for advancement and profession improvement, and to have the option to seek after their achievements over a long haul vocation life, instead of in the short run.

McWilliams and Siegel (2001) studied that corporate social responsibility is subsumed by wider notion of accountability. Lerner & Tetlock(1999) studied that objective condition is important in accountability. Employees may fail to get recognition on their importance. Lewin(1936) studied that it is not necessary for objective reality to drive cognitions and behaviors but rather individuals` subjective interpretation of the same. It is also studied that employees` subjective interpretations of such objective mechanism which is a matter in terms of employees` behavioral responses. Hall et al (2017) studied that organizations might induce or create informal accountability norms which helps management to defend unethical or illegal behavior to stakeholders as well as employees.

Wilk S L et al (2005) studied that Green Display Rules(GDR) administer as the apparent activity requests for representatives to show green-related practices in organization. The job demand approach took into consideration fluctuation in the relational necessities of work to exist inside word related classifications and dwell in explicit employments. Salancik G.R.et al (1978) studied that employee is asset of organization and every employee has right to ask for right job. Employee can ask for better interpersonal demands which may be resulted in legitimate in view of supervisor or immediate superior of employee. Such demands are related with social information processing theory. Social information processing theory proposes that employees` view of occupation requests are impacted by what individuals around them think. As it were, representatives assemble their recognitions and mentalities in the public arena dependent on meaningful gestures in the work environment. Grant A L et al (2009) studied that importance and significance of relational work prerequisites may trigger employee self-guideline exercises to screen their own consistence with display rules. Accordingly, relevant factors, for example, display rules assume a significant job in enacting esteems and reinforcing or debilitating values to behavior relationships.

Thus, the above previous literature published by researchers, academicians as well as scholars help to identify the research gaps on association amongst EGB, WV, FA and GDR. The objectives constituted as follows are as result of the literature reviewed.

3. OBJECTIVES

1. To study the relationship between employee green behavior and work values
2. To validate the role of felt accountability in relations between employee green behavior and work values.
3. To justify the role of green display rules in relations between employee green behavior and work values.

4. HYPOTHESES

H01: Employee Green behavior (EGB) and Work Values (WVs) are not associated with each other.

H02: No relations between employee green behavior (EGB) and Felt Accountability

H03: No relations between employee green behavior (EGB) and Green Display Rules

5. MEASURES

The present survey was conducted amongst employees of IT, ITeS and Banking sector employees working in Bangalore city (n=398).The structured questionnaires employed to the respondents with 5-point Likert scale (SDA-SA)The collected data with 46 items of four

factors (EGB₁₋₁₄, WV₁₋₁₀, F A₁₋₁₂ and GDR₁₋₁₀) are standardized. The demographic results demonstrate on gender (Male= 56.3% Female=43.7%), age (≤ 35 yrs=48.7%, 35-50 yrs=30.2%, 50yrs+ =21.1%) and education (graduate=38.9%,PG=61.1%) Cronbach alpha (α) observed as 0.895(89.5%) for EGB, 0.794(79.4%) for WV, 0.855(85.5%) for FA and 0.819(81.9%) for GDR.No item is excluded during item wise analysis by using IBMSPSS.25 as a statistical tool.

The results of descriptive statistics indicate N=398, minimum is 1 and maximum is 5, mean is observed within the range of 2.96 to 3.32.whereas SD is within the range of 1.13 to 1.64 for Employee Green Behavior (EGB₁₋₁₄).The results on minimum and maximum are same for the rest of the three factors (i.e.WV₁₋₁₀,FA₁₋₁₀ and GD₁₋₁₀) The output on descriptive statistics suggests to move on for further analysis.

5.1. Hypotheses Testing

H₀1: Employee Green behavior (EGB) and Work Values (WVs) are not associated with each other.

H₁1: Employee Green behavior (EGB) and Work Values (WVs) are positively associated with each other.

The following results are obtained on conducting Pearson Correlations test for the purpose of examining the relationship between employee green behavior (EGB) and work values (WV).

Correlations(Table-1)

		EGB	WV
EGB	Pearson Correlation	1	.943**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
WV	Pearson Correlation	.943**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlations computed between two factors (EGB₁₋₁₄, WV₁₋₁₀,) on data for 398 valid respondents. The results suggest that EGB₁₋₁₄ and WV₁₋₁₀ are measured r (Pearson coefficient) as 0.943(94.3%) with significance level at 0.00($p \leq 0.05$) In this case, we have rejected H₀1 and H₁1 is accepted. The results on scatterplot on association between employee green behavior and work value is obtained in the following manner.(Fig.2)

Figure 2 Associations between employee green behavior and work value

The following results are obtained on conducting Pearson Correlations test for the purpose of examining the relationship between employee green behavior (EGB) and felt accountability (FA).

H₀2: No relations between employee green behavior (EGB) and Felt Accountability

H₁2: Employee green behavior (EGB) and Felt Accountability (FA) are positively associated with each other.

		EGB	FA
EGB	Pearson Correlation	1	.819**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
FA	Pearson Correlation	.819**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlations computed between two factors (EGB₁₋₁₄, FA₁₋₁₂) on data for 398 valid respondents. The results suggest that EGB₁₋₁₄ and FA₁₋₁₂ are measured r (Pearson coefficient) as 0.819(81.9%) with significance level at 0.00(p≤0.05) In this case, we have rejected H₀2 and H₁2 is accepted. The result on scatterplot on association between employee green behavior and felt accountability is obtained in the following manner (Fig.3) (S. Dixit et al., 2018; Saurav Dixit, Mandal, Thanikal, & Saurabh, 2019; Saurav Dixit, Sharma, & Singh, 2020; Saurav Dixit & Sharma, 2020; Shah, Dixit, Kumar, Jain, & Anand, 2019).

Figure 2 Association between employee green behavior and felt accountability

The following results are obtained on conducting Pearson Correlations test for the purpose of examining the relationship between employee green behavior (EGB) and green display rules (GDR)

		EGB	GD
EGB	Pearson Correlation	1	.835**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
GDR	Pearson Correlation	.835**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlations computed between two factors (EGB₁₋₁₄, GD₁₋₁₀) on data for 398 valid respondents. The results suggest that EGB₁₋₁₄ and GD₁₋₁₀ are measured r (Pearson coefficient) as 0.835(83.5%) with significance level at 0.00($p \leq 0.05$) In this case, we have rejected H₀₃ and H₁₃ is accepted.

The result on scatterplot on association between employee green behavior and green display rules is obtained in the following manner (Fig.4)

Figure 4 Association between employee green behavior and green display

6. CONCLUSION

Companies are progressively being constrained to boost companies' environmental performance. Evidence from the present investigation proposes that including felt responsibility (FA) and green display rules (GDR) may add to employee's voluntary green work place behavior. For instance, when an organizational website or virtually board release distributes standards and prerequisites for environmental protection and asset reusing, employees who focus on their own inclinations and interests can be progressively mindful of their work values and job requirement. In this way, employees are bound to agree to with the workplace rules. The study also concludes that relations amongst employee green behavior (EGB), work values (WV), felt accountability (FA) and green display behavior (GDR) are significantly positively associated with each other and such relations cannot be ignored during the study.

7. LIMITATIONS AND SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The present study is a humble try to know about promoting employees environmentally free behavior in limited sectors of Bangalore city such as IT sector. ITeS sector and banking sector. The survey can be extended to other areas with more sample size and factors of primary data source. The present study also represents one country and one city work environment. It means cross-cultural environment at work place is not taken into consideration.

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